

Sonalika (HD 1553) was sown on 30 Nov 1981 and Kalyan Sona (HD1593) on 11 Dec 1982 in 5- × 2-m plots in a randomized block design replicated 3 times. Seed rate was 100 kg/ha.

In both years, panicle length, spikelet number, number of spikelets per panicle, and test weight of wheat were significantly related to fertilizer level (Table 2).

Grain and straw yields responded significantly to fertilizer application during both years. The highest yields of grain and straw were at 120-27-50 kg NPK/ha. □

Table 2. Effect of fertilizer on yield and yield-attributing characters of wheat following rice. Madhya Pradesh, India, 1981-83.

Treatment (kg/ha)			1981-82 (Sonalika HD1553)					1982-83 (K. Sona HD1593)				
N	P	K	Grain yield (t/ha)	Length of panicles (cm)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Spikelets /panicle	1000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Length of panicles (cm)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Spikelets /panicle	1000-grain wt (g)
0	0	0	1.1	6.9	13.1	36.4	33.2	0.7	7.9	13.2	31.7	32.0
40	0	0	1.6	7.8	14.5	44.6	35.2	1.3	8.4	14.6	42.2	35.0
80	0	0	1.9	8.1	15.5	45.4	33.6	1.9	9.3	16.0	51.0	34.8
120	0	0	2.5	8.5	16.4	55.2	35.1	2.3	9.7	17.2	55.2	34.6
40	9	0	1.6	7.7	14.8	44.6	34.4	1.5	8.7	15.0	43.6	33.8
80	18	0	1.9	8.4	15.7	48.0	35.6	1.8	9.3	15.8	47.1	35.6
120	27	0	2.8	8.4	17.9	52.4	35.9	2.4	9.9	16.5	51.3	36.5
40	9	17	1.5	7.3	14.4	39.9	34.9	1.2	8.5	14.9	39.4	34.5
80	18	33	1.9	7.6	15.6	50.9	36.6	2.0	9.4	15.8	50.2	36.4
120	27	50	3.1	8.3	15.4	51.1	36.1	2.4	9.3	15.7	49.5	35.2
LSD (0.05)			0.4	0.6	1.4	6.3	1.2	0.5	0.7	1.2	7.5	2.0

Effect of zinc and phosphorus on rice - wheat yields in semireclaimed alkali soil

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Most alkali soils of the Indo-Gangetic plains are rich in available P but deficient in available Zn. When soils are reclaimed, P availability decreases because of leaching, formation of calcium phosphates, and crop uptakes. At the same time, continuous Zn application results in a high buildup of available Zn in the soils. This disproportionate availability of Zn and P may affect crop growth and plant chemical composition.

A long-term field experiment in a split-plot design with four replications studied the effect of applied Zn on yields in loamy alkali soil. The soil was treated with gypsum (14 t/ha) and cropped in a rice (Jaya) - wheat (HD2009) sequence. After the fourth rice crop, 18 kg/ha was added to one-half of each plot.

Zn significantly increased wheat yield (see table). P application had no effect, even in the sixth year of reclamation. Rice responded

Effect of Zn and P fertilizer on grain yields of rice and wheat and on DTPA-extractable Zn at harvest of the 6th rice crop in reclaimed alkali soil. Karnal, India.

Zinc added (kg/ha)	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)								DTPA - Zn (mg/kg) at 6th rice	
	Rice				Wheat				WP	P
	1st WP	4th WP	5th	6th	6th	6th	WP	P		
0	5.06	4.99	5.16	5.37	4.87	5.19	2.56	2.60	0.52	0.56
2	6.01	5.98	5.14	6.12	5.14	6.42	3.33	3.38	3.20	3.14
4	6.04	6.19	5.53	6.15	5.31	6.37	3.38	3.42	5.10	4.92
9	6.00	6.11	5.42	6.24	5.34	6.76	3.29	3.46	9.52	9.36
18	6.00	6.18	5.46	6.08	5.27	6.85	3.08	3.21	15.84	13.72
27	5.97	6.08	5.47	6.24	5.30	6.69	3.05	3.29	23.88	19.05
Mean	5.85	5.92	5.41	6.03	5.21	6.38	3.12	3.23	9.63	8.46
LSD (0.05)										
Zn	0.62	0.26	0.39		0.68		0.38		2.07	
P	—	—	0.22		0.37		ns		0.82	
Zn × P	—	—	ns		ns		ns		2.01	

^a WP = without phosphorus, P = with phosphorus.

significantly to Zn and P applied together after the fourth year. P or Zn alone gave significantly lower yields than P and Zn together. Zn and P significantly increased nutrient uptake by both crops.

The optimum fertilizer for a rice - wheat sequence was 2 kg Zn/ha. Higher applications increased DTPA-extractable Zn up to 23.88 mg/kg and had a residual effect on succeeding

crops with no deleterious effect on yields. However, 18 kg Zn/ha significantly reduced available Fe. Application of 18 kg P/ha significantly reduced DTPA-extractable Zn by about 20% but increased P availability.

These results suggest that P application to wheat can be deferred to the sixth year of reclamation, but 18 kg P/ha and 2 kg Zn/ha are essential for rice after the fourth year. □